

Mutli-Task, Transformer-Based Prediction of Chronic Ischemic Heart Disease from Sequential ECG Data with Continuous-Time Positional Embedding

Alexander Ye, Magdalena Bak, Emily Tung, Jonathan David Gonzalez Gomez, Mehmet Fatih Akcaoglu

National Taiwan University

Taipei, Taiwan

Abstract—Heart disease remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, claiming approximately 19.2 million lives in 2023. Traditional risk assessment tools suffer from limitations including static evaluation approaches, high diagnostic costs, and inability to capture disease progression over time. In this paper, we propose a transformer-based deep learning model that leverages sequential electrocardiogram (ECG) data to predict chronic ischemic heart disease (ICD-10: I25) within 6-month, 1-year, and 3-year time windows. Our approach integrates Continuous-Time Linear Positional Embedding (CTLPE) to explicitly model irregular time intervals between ECG measurements, addressing a key challenge in clinical time-series data. Using the ECG-VIEW II dataset comprising 461,178 patients and 979,273 ECG records from a South Korean hospital over a 19-year period, we demonstrate that our multi-task temporal model significantly outperforms both static machine learning baselines and sequential deep learning models. Specifically, our model achieves an AUROC of 0.9 for 1-year prediction compared to 0.769 for XGBoost and 0.888 for standard GRU models. Furthermore, multi-task learning across prediction horizons yields improved performance over single-task approaches, with the multi-task model achieving higher AUROC across all time horizons. These results suggest that transformer-based architectures with appropriate temporal encoding can effectively capture disease progression patterns from routine ECG measurements, offering a cost-effective and scalable approach for cardiovascular risk stratification.

Keywords—transformer, ECG prediction, ischemic heart disease, continuous-time embedding, multi-task learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death globally, with approximately 19.2 million deaths in 2023 [1]. Chronic ischemic heart disease poses a significant burden, often progressing silently before acute events. Early identification of at-risk individuals enables timely intervention and improves outcomes.

Current clinical practice relies on static risk assessment tools and diagnostic methods like echocardiography. However, these approaches have critical limitations: static models capture only a single snapshot of patient health, advanced tests incur substantial costs (~\$500), and existing tools cannot leverage temporal patterns in longitudinal data [2].

The electrocardiogram (ECG) offers a compelling alternative: widely available, inexpensive (~\$50), and non-invasive. Recent AI advances have shown that ECG signals contain rich prognostic information, successfully predicting ejection fraction, atrial fibrillation, and structural abnormalities [3]. However, most AI-ECG approaches analyze single recordings, neglecting temporal information from multiple examinations over time.

Modeling sequential clinical data with irregular time intervals remains challenging. Traditional recurrent neural networks assume regular sampling, making them suboptimal for clinical data where measurements occur at varying intervals. Recent work has introduced time-aware decay functions and continuous-time positional encodings to address this [4, 5].

In this paper, we propose a transformer-based architecture for irregularly-sampled ECG time series. Our key contributions are:

- A multi-horizon prediction framework estimating chronic ischemic heart disease risk at 6-month, 1-year, and 3-year windows simultaneously.
- Integration of Continuous-Time Linear Positional Embedding (CTLPE) to explicitly model variable time intervals between ECG measurements.
- Extensive experiments demonstrating substantial improvement over both static models and sequential deep learning methods.
- Model interpretation through feature importance and calibration analysis, providing clinical insights into predictions.

II. RELATED WORK

A. AI-ECG for Cardiovascular Prediction

The application of deep learning to ECG analysis has demonstrated remarkable success across various cardiovascular conditions. Attia et al. [3] developed a convolutional neural network that predicts left ventricular ejection fraction from 12-lead ECG with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.86, demonstrating that ECG contains information about cardiac structure not apparent to human readers. Subsequent work has

extended AI-ECG to predict atrial fibrillation [6], age and sex [7], and all-cause mortality [8].

However, the majority of these approaches analyze single ECG recordings without considering temporal evolution. Hsu et al. [9] recently addressed this limitation in the context of stroke prediction for atrial fibrillation patients. Their ForeSIIN (Forecasting Stroke with Independent and Interpretable Networks) model employs independent GRU cells for each clinical feature, reducing feature interference while handling missing data. While this work demonstrates the value of temporal modeling for cardiovascular outcomes, it relies on recurrent architectures that may struggle with long-range dependencies and does not explicitly model irregular time intervals between observations.

B. Handling Irregular Time Series in Clinical Data

Real-world clinical time series present unique challenges including irregular sampling intervals, missing values, and informative missingness patterns. Che et al. [4] introduced GRU-D, a model that treats missingness as a signal rather than merely an error. The key insight is that the time interval between observations and which variables are missing reflect underlying patient state. GRU-D incorporates learnable decay rates within the GRU cell structure, allowing the model to learn how quickly information fades based on elapsed time. This approach achieved strong performance on clinical prediction tasks from the MIMIC-III dataset.

Building on this foundation, Kim and Lee [5] proposed Continuous-Time Linear Positional Embedding (CTLPE) specifically for irregular time series forecasting in transformer architectures. CTLPE learns position embeddings combining a linear decay/growth term with standard periodic components, adapting to inconsistent observation patterns. This approach achieved state-of-the-art results on multiple time series benchmarks and directly informs our architectural choices.

C. Transformer Architectures for Time Series

The transformer architecture [10] has revolutionized sequence modeling through its self-attention mechanism, enabling parallel computation and effective capture of long-range dependencies. Nie et al. [11] introduced PatchTST, achieving a 21% reduction in mean squared error compared to previous transformer models. PatchTST segments time series into patches, applies channel-independent processing, and employs masked self-supervised pre-training. While PatchTST demonstrates transformers' potential for time series, it targets forecasting rather than classification and assumes regularly-sampled data. Our work adapts transformer concepts for clinical risk classification with explicit handling of irregular sampling.

D. Multi-Task Learning for Clinical Outcomes

Clinical prediction often involves multiple related outcomes that may share underlying risk factors. Yoon et al. [12] recently presented a multicenter validation of a scalable, interpretable, multitask prediction model. Their Multi-Task LightGBM architecture employs shared lower layers to learn common risk patterns across outcomes while task-specific upper layers capture outcome-unique patterns. The model achieved strong external validation performance across three hospitals, demonstrating the approach's generalizability. We adopt similar principles for our prediction framework.

E. ECG Features and Biomarkers in Heart Failure

Understanding which ECG parameters carry prognostic significance guides feature selection and model interpretation. Chetran et al. [13] conducted a pilot study examining ECG and biomarker profiles in acute heart failure patients, finding that 81.6% of patients exhibited both ECG abnormalities and elevated biomarkers. QTc prolongation, present in 11.1% of patients in our dataset, has been linked to drug-induced arrhythmia risk, while PR interval abnormalities are associated with 45% higher atrial fibrillation risk. These clinical findings support our use of ECG-derived parameters as predictive features.

III. METHOD

We propose a transformer-based architecture for irregularly-sampled ECG time series that uses Continuous-Time Linear Positional Embedding (CTLPE) to model variable time intervals between measurements. This approach combines sequential ECG feature encoding with temporal modeling to predict chronic ischemic heart disease across multiple time horizons.

A. Problem Formulation

Let $X = \{(x_1, t_1), (x_2, t_2), \dots, (x_n, t_n)\}$ represent a patient's ECG sequence, where $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the i -th ECG feature vector with $d=10$ features (RR, PR, QRS, QT, QTc, P-axis, QRS-axis, T-axis, sex, age) and t_i represents the timestamp in days from the first ECG. The time intervals between consecutive ECGs are irregular: $\Delta t_i = t_{i+1} - t_i$, where Δt_i varies across patients and within individual sequences.

Our objective is to predict the risk of chronic ischemic heart disease (ICD-10: I25) within three prediction windows $W \in \{6 \text{ months}, 1 \text{ year}, 3 \text{ years}\}$ after the last observed ECG. For each prediction window $w \in W$, we learn a function $f_\theta: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ that maps the ECG sequence to a probability. We employ a multi-task learning framework where all three prediction horizons share the same feature encoder while maintaining task-specific prediction heads.

B. Architecture Overview

Our model architecture consists of four main components: (1) ECG feature embedding with missingness handling, (2) CTLPE-based temporal encoding, (3) Transformer encoder, and (4) multi-task

prediction heads. The pipeline processes variable-length ECG sequences and outputs simultaneous risk predictions for all three temporal horizons.

Fig. 1. The overall architecture of the proposed model.

C. ECG Feature Embedding

Following the approach in GRU-D [4], we treat missingness as an informative signal. For each ECG observation x_i , we create a dual-channel representation: a value channel with missing values replaced by zero ($\tilde{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$), and a mask channel with binary indicators of observed features ($m_i \in \{0,1\}^d$). The dual-channel representation is concatenated to form a 2d-dimensional input vector $[\tilde{x}_i; m_i] \in \mathbb{R}^{2d}$, which is then projected to the model's hidden dimension through a linear embedding layer: $e_i = W_e[\tilde{x}_i; m_i] + b_e$, where $d_{model} = 128$ is the model dimension.

Note that while zero-imputation is used here, there exists potential ambiguity when true ECG values are near zero, which we address through the explicit mask channel.

D. Continuous-Time Linear Positional Embedding

Standard positional encodings in transformers assume regular, discrete positions. However, clinical ECG measurements occur at irregular intervals. We adopt CTLPE [5], which explicitly encodes continuous time information. CTLPE decomposes the temporal encoding into two components: $p_i(t) = p_{linear}(t) + p_{periodic}(t)$. The linear component models monotonic temporal trends: $p_{linear}(t) = \alpha_{linear} \cdot t$, where α_{linear} is a learnable weight vector. The periodic component preserves the ability to model cyclic temporal patterns using sine and cosine functions. In our implementation, we use $d_{model} = 128$, allocating 64 dimensions to linear encoding and 64 to periodic encoding.

E. Transformer Encoder

The temporally-encoded sequence $H = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n\}$ is processed through a standard transformer encoder with multi-head self-attention. The

self-attention mechanism allows the model to learn complex dependencies between ECG measurements at different time points. We use 4 attention heads and 3 transformer layers with a feedforward dimension of 512. Layer normalization and residual connections are applied following standard transformer architecture. To handle variable-length sequences, we employ padding masks that prevent the model from attending to padded positions.

F. Sequence Pooling and Prediction Heads

After the transformer encoder, we apply last-token pooling to obtain a fixed-dimensional representation $z \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{model}}$ from the variable-length sequence. Last-token pooling selects the hidden state corresponding to the final ECG measurement, which contains the most recent clinical information. The pooled representation z is passed to three task-specific prediction heads, one for each temporal horizon: $\hat{y}_w = \sigma(W_w \cdot z + b_w)$, where σ is the sigmoid activation function.

G. Training Objective

We train the model using a multi-task binary cross-entropy loss that combines prediction losses across all three temporal horizons. We use equal weights $\lambda_w = 1/3$ for all tasks, treating each prediction horizon with equal importance. The multi-task formulation encourages the shared feature encoder to learn representations that are informative for risk assessment across multiple time scales.

IV. EXPERIMENT SETUPS AND DATASETS

A. Dataset Description

We utilize the ECG-VIEW II dataset, a comprehensive longitudinal collection from a South Korean hospital spanning a 19-year period (2000-2019). The dataset consisted of 461,178 patients with 979,273 ECG records and 7,743,772 total clinical records including diagnoses and medication data.

Each ECG record contains 8 clinical measurements: RR interval, PR interval, QRS duration, QT interval, QTc (corrected QT), P-wave axis, QRS axis, and T-wave axis. Patient age and biological sex are included as additional features. Disease diagnoses are coded using ICD-10, with focus on chronic ischemic heart disease (I25). The dataset contains 73,532 I25 diagnosis records across 7,315 unique patients.

B. Data Preprocessing and Cohort Selection

We restrict analysis to patients with at least 2 ECG measurements within a 2-year window, yielding 50,921 patients suitable for time-series modeling. To prevent data leakage, we exclude patients diagnosed with I25 within 30 days of an ECG measurement. For each patient's final ECG, we create binary labels for three prediction windows (6-month, 1-year, 3-year). The dataset exhibits substantial missingness in certain ECG parameters; rather than removing incomplete records, we employ zero-imputation with explicit mask

channels allowing the model to learn from missingness patterns.

TABLE I
Missing Value Statistics Across ECG Features

Feature	Missing Count	Missing Percentage (%)
RR	34	0
PR	205,013	20.94
QRS	168,900	17.25
QT	0	0
QTc	0	0
P_wave_axis	246,446	25.17
QRS_axis	216,999	22.16
T_wave_axis	217,025	22.16
ACCI	0	0

C. Train-Validation-Test Split

We employ a temporal split strategy to ensure realistic evaluation. Patients are sorted by the date of their last ECG measurement and divided into: Training set (60%, earliest measurements), Validation set (20%, middle period), and Test set (20%, most recent measurements). This temporal split simulates real-world deployment where models trained on historical data must predict outcomes for new patients.

D. Baseline Models

We compare our approach against two categories of baselines. Static Machine Learning Models use only the most recent ECG measurement: Logistic Regression (L2 regularization, $C=1.0$) and XGBoost (100 estimators, max depth 6, learning rate 0.1). Sequential Deep Learning Models process the full ECG sequence: RNN (128 hidden units), LSTM (128 hidden units), and GRU (128 hidden units). All sequential models use the same dual-channel feature embedding and last-token pooling strategy as our transformer model for fair comparison.

E. Implementation Details

Our transformer model uses $d_{model} = 128$ dimensions, 3 encoder layers, 4 attention heads, feedforward dimension 512, and dropout rate 0.1. We train for 50 epochs using the Adam optimizer with learning rate 0.001 and batch size 32. Early stopping with patience of 10 epochs is applied based on validation AUROC. Model performance is assessed using AUROC (Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristic) and AUPRC (Area Under Precision-Recall Curve). We report metrics averaged over 3 random seeds to account for training variability.

F. Ablation Studies

To validate design choices, we conduct ablation studies examining: (1) Single-task vs. Multi-task

Learning, (2) CTLPE vs. Standard Positional Encoding, and (3) Missingness Handling approaches (zero-imputation with mask channels versus mean imputation).

V. RESULTS

A. Comparison with Baseline Models

Table II presents the performance comparison between our transformer-based model and static machine learning baselines for 1-year I25 prediction. Our model achieves an AUROC of 0.9000, substantially outperforming both Logistic Regression (0.7537) and XGBoost (0.7686). The improvement in AUPRC is even more pronounced, with our model achieving 0.2471 compared to 0.0453 and 0.0566 for the baseline models, respectively. These results demonstrate the value of sequential modeling over static approaches.

TABLE II
Performance Comparison: Static ML vs. Our Model (1-Year Prediction)

Model	AUROC	AUPRC
Logistic Regression	0.7537	0.0453
XGBoost	0.7686	0.0566
Ours (Transformer+CTLPE)	0.9000	0.2471

B. Comparison with Sequential Deep Learning Models

Table III compares our model against sequential deep learning baselines (RNN, LSTM, GRU) across all three prediction horizons. Our transformer-based model with CTLPE achieves the highest AUROC across all time windows: 0.8953 (6-month), 0.9000 (1-year), and 0.8963 (3-year). The consistent improvement over recurrent architectures demonstrates the effectiveness of self-attention mechanisms and continuous-time positional encoding for capturing temporal patterns in irregularly-sampled ECG data.

TABLE III
Performance Across Multiple Prediction Horizons

Model	6-month	1-year	3-year
RNN	0.8715	0.8752	0.8892
LSTM	0.8828	0.8877	0.89
GRU	0.8821	0.8881	0.8902
Ours	0.8953	0.9	0.8963

VI. Discussion

To understand the clinical relevance of our model's predictions, we conducted feature importance analysis and calibration assessment for the 1-year ischemic heart disease prediction task.

A. Feature Importance Analysis

We evaluated feature importance by measuring the decrease in AUROC when each feature was permuted. The QT interval emerged as the most influential feature with an AUC increase of 0.269, substantially higher than all other features. This finding aligns with clinical knowledge, as prolonged QT interval is associated with increased cardiovascular risk and arrhythmia susceptibility [13]. Age ranked second in importance (AUC increase: 0.048), followed by QTc (0.033) and RR interval (0.022). Sex contributed moderately to predictions (0.021), consistent with known sex-based differences in cardiovascular disease presentation.

Fig. 2. ROC curves for 6-month, 1-year, and 3-year I25 predictions. Our model demonstrates consistent discrimination ability across all prediction horizons with AUROC values exceeding 0.89.

Fig. 3. Precision-Recall curves for 6-month, 1-year, and 3-year I25 predictions. The model maintains high precision at various recall levels, particularly for longer prediction windows.

C. Multi-Task vs. Single-Task Learning

Table IV presents the ablation study comparing single-task and multi-task learning approaches. The multi-task model achieves higher AUROC across all time horizons: 0.8953 vs. 0.8746 (6-month), 0.9000 vs. 0.8880 (1-year), and 0.8963 vs. 0.8926 (3-year). While the single-task model shows slightly higher AUPRC for 1-year prediction (0.2600 vs. 0.2471), the multi-task approach demonstrates superior discrimination ability overall, validating our hypothesis that shared representations across temporal horizons improve risk prediction.

TABLE IV

Single-Task vs. Multi-Task Learning Performance.

Model	6-month	1-year	3-year
Single-Task	0.8746	0.888	0.8926
Multi-Task	0.8953	0.9	0.8963

Fig. 4. Feature importance for 1-year I25 prediction.

B. Model Calibration

The calibration curve comparing predicted risk probabilities against actual observed risk demonstrates reasonable calibration across the probability range. A well-calibrated model should follow the diagonal line representing perfect calibration. Our model shows slight underestimation at very low risk levels and moderate deviation in mid-range probabilities (2-4%), but maintains good agreement at higher risk thresholds (8-10%). This calibration performance suggests that the model's probability outputs can provide clinically meaningful risk estimates for patient stratification.

Fig. 5. Calibration curve of the proposed model. The plot compares the predicted risk probabilities against the actual observed frequencies.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have presented a transformer-based deep learning model that leverages sequential ECG data with continuous-time positional embedding to predict chronic ischemic heart disease across multiple time horizons. Our approach demonstrates substantial improvements over both static machine learning baselines and sequential deep learning models, achieving an AUROC of 0.9 for 1-year prediction. The integration of CTLPE effectively captures irregular temporal patterns in clinical data, while multi-task learning across prediction horizons improves performance. These results suggest that transformer-based architectures with appropriate temporal encoding can effectively capture disease progression patterns from routine ECG measurements, offering a cost-effective and scalable approach for cardiovascular risk stratification. Future work will explore the application of this framework to other cardiovascular conditions and investigate the integration of additional clinical variables beyond ECG measurements.

A. Limitations and Future Work

Our study has some limitations that require further consideration. First, our zero-imputation strategy for missing ECG values, while paired with explicit mask channels, may introduce ambiguity when true ECG measurements are close to zero. Alternative imputation strategies such as using -1 or learned embeddings for missing values could be explored in future work to eliminate this potential confusion between actual zero values and imputed missing data. Second, our model was trained and evaluated on data from a single South Korean hospital, which may limit generalizability to other populations and healthcare settings. Third, while our model achieves strong discrimination performance, real-world deployment would require careful consideration of calibration across different patient subgroups and clinical contexts.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Alex- Project conceptualization and pivot from planned NTUH data to ECG-ViEW II dataset, development of complete data preprocessing pipeline including imputation strategy and data leakage prevention methods, implementation of initial backbone transformer model architecture for subsequent iterations, development and evaluation of baseline static machine learning models (Logistic Regression and XGBoost), contribution of all literature survey papers for the final presentation, leadership of presentation pitch and Q&A sessions, and substantial contributions to slide preparation across all three semester presentations

Magda - Implementation of Continuous-Time Linear Positional Embedding (CTLPE) for I25 prediction, exploration of different imputation methods including SMOTE, hyperparameter tuning of CTLPE, integration of CTLPE with multi-horizon prediction framework, preparation of presentation slides and the final report.

Emily - Implemented a multi-task prediction framework that combines multi-label comorbidity classification with risk forecasting for I25 and I10 over 6-month, 1-year, and 3-year intervals. The model was evaluated against baseline RNN, LSTM, and GRU architectures, and ablation studies were conducted to compare single-task and multi-task learning objectives. Additional contributions included preparing the project proposal, paper survey, final presentation slides, and refining the final report format.

Jonathan - Contribution to the initial data exploration and problem formulation, conducting analyses to understand the ECG ViEW-II dataset characteristics and clinical prediction challenges. Development of a baseline model and participation in the literature survey through identification and evaluation of papers that informed our methodological approaches. Experimentation with various model architectures and optimization strategies throughout implementation to improve predictive performance.

Fatih - Exploration of basic static ML models. Implementation of feature importance analysis and risk assessment (latter is not included in the report) for the single-task model. Lastly, contribution to the final report with Introduction and related work parts.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organization, "Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs)," WHO Fact Sheet, 2023. [Online]. Available: [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
- [2] P. W. F. Wilson et al., "Prediction of coronary heart disease using risk factor categories," *Circulation*, vol. 97, no. 18, pp. 1837–1847, 1998.
- [3] Z. I. Attia et al., "An artificial intelligence-enabled ECG algorithm for the identification of patients with atrial fibrillation during sinus rhythm: a retrospective analysis of outcome prediction," *The Lancet*, vol. 394, no. 10201, pp. 861–867, 2019.
- [4] Z. Che, S. Purushotham, K. Cho, D. Sontag, and Y. Liu, "Recurrent neural networks for multivariate time series with missing values," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 6085, 2018.
- [5] B. Kim and J.-G. Lee, "Continuous-time linear positional embedding for irregular time series forecasting," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.20092*, 2024.
- [6] S. Raghunath et al., "Deep neural networks can predict new-onset atrial fibrillation from the 12-lead ECG and help identify those at risk of atrial fibrillation-related stroke," *Circulation*, vol. 143, no. 13, pp. 1287–1298, 2021.
- [7] Z. I. Attia et al., "Age and sex estimation using artificial intelligence from standard 12-lead ECGs," *Circulation: Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology*, vol. 12, no. 9, p. e007284, 2019.
- [8] S. Raghunath et al., "Prediction of mortality from 12-lead electrocardiogram voltage data using a deep neural network," *Nature Medicine*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 886–891, 2020.

- [9] J.-C. Hsu, Y.-H. Hseih, Y.-Y. Yang, S.-L. Chuang, C. Lin, and L.-Y. Lin, "Interpretable independent recurrent networks for forecasting stroke in atrial fibrillation," *JACC: Asia*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 966–978, 2025.
- [10] A. Vaswani et al., "Attention is all you need," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
- [11] Y. Nie, N. H. Nguyen, P. Sinthong, and J. Kalagnanam, "A time series is worth 64 words: Long-term forecasting with transformers," in *Proc. Int. Conf. on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2023.
- [12] H.-K. Yoon et al., "Multicenter validation of a scalable, interpretable, multitask prediction model for multiple clinical outcomes," *npj Digital Medicine*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2025.
- [13] A. Chetran et al., "ECG and biomarker profile in patients with acute heart failure: A pilot study," *Diagnostics*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 1467, 2022.